

**HISTORICAL IN THE FORMATION OF MORAL THINKING IN YOUTH
PLACE OF MONUMENTS: IMAM AL-BUKHARY MEMORIAL
COMPLEX.**

Kamoliddinov Shavkat

a student of the National Independence Idea, Spiritual Foundations and Law
Education, Faculty of History, Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

ANNOTATION: In this article, reconstruction works of the memorial complex of Imam al-Bukhari after independence and studying the works of Imam al-Bukhari, researching them, as well as physical and legal entities moral among young people by studying Islamic manuscripts, petroglyphs Concepts are a struggle against the dogmatic ideas of religious ekremism. Shaping our national values, on the formation of a sense of pride in contributing to the world science culture the researcher expressed his thoughts.

KEY WORDS: Scientific research center, UNESCO, Oxford, religious extremism, religious extremism, national value education, neighborhood.

After the independence of our country, special attention was paid to the Imam al-Bukhari memorial complex began to focus. Instead of the mausoleum of Allolma, who dedicated his whole life to knowledge like Imam Bukhari The memorial complex was built. The mausoleum of our Allama, who spread faith, faith, knowledge, knowledge, Samarkand It is located in the village of Khoja Ismail, Payarik District, Imam Bukhari Memorial Complex First President of the Republic of Kazakhstan I.AKarimov. The construction of the mausoleum It is typical of the Central Asian style In addition, experts from abroad were invited in the construction of the complex. Including UNESCO experts Prince Charles of Wales Institute of Architecture Oxford Islam specialists of the research center were involved. Total land allocated for the memorial complex The area is 10 hectares. The mausoleum of Imam al-Bukhari is located in the main part of the complex. The mausoleum is made of marble. It is symbolic. The original tomb of Imam Bukhari is located under it. A mosque for 1500 people was built next to the mausoleum. There are three entrances to the architectural building of the complex It is carried out through an arched gate. 1225th anniversary was widely celebrated in 1998 on the basis of the decision to "celebrate the anniversary." Imam al-Bukhari and an international scientific conference will be held on the topic of his role in world culture".

International scientific research center under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan decision of March 27, 2017 was adopted. distributes information about the essence and religion of Islam. Imam Bukhari, the great scholar of the Islamic world widely promoting scientific and spiritual heritage, creative activities and spiritual-educational heritage among young people Prevents the

slanders that are being made to the minds of young people today without any basis in Islam getting, religious extremism, bigotry, false cults and today's youth easily develops the scientific and educational foundations of the fight against joining extremist groups. The center is its own During its activity, it is engaged in the purchase and analysis of Islamic books belonging to individuals and legal entities. Another task assigned to the center is interreligious and to convey the values of inter-ethnic tolerance, mutual respect and understanding to the general public will help.

President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev during his visit to Samarkand on February 11, 2021 Reconstruction of the Imam Bukhari memorial complex was carried out informed about the improvement works. According to the project, a mosque with a capacity of 8,000 thousand seats will be built. Complex four huge towers will be built around it. There are also hotels for foreign pilgrims will be done.

The implementation of such works is the attention paid to our national values and traditions, Islam the further development of religion is an example of the attention paid to our historical monuments. In order to prevent young people from joining religious extremist groups today help them to understand the true nature of Islam.

Islamic scholars of the Middle Ages and thinkers of hadith studies, kalam, (science of theology), jurisprudence (Islamic law) and Islamic history for further research of religious and spiritual heritage implements related projects. By organizing a harmonious study of rich cultural heritage, secular and religious sciences organizational-practical in applying its results in the educational process and conveying them to the general public will help.

Giving Islamic concepts in the formation of moral thinking. Understanding its essence and correct interpretation.

A state of mind achieved in moral life or through study and family education In one of the hadiths, the Prophet said, "A Muslim with good character is the most perfect in terms of faith. is a Muslim" they said.

Religion is the relationship between people and God, and the relationship between people and people defined. Expanding the moral thinking of our youth to enrich their moral and aesthetic concepts in the family, in the neighborhood, in the school, we need to form our national values, the concepts of manners and ethics. Because Our people have always paid great attention to the morals and spirituality of young people. West Unlike other countries, we treat youth education separately. Our first president is Islam As Karimov said: "Uzbekistan's future greatness depends first of all on the spiritual, moral, is closely connected with the political and aesthetic maturity". of our historical monuments in inculcating the inherited national traditions and values and its place is incomparable.

In his youth, Imam al-Bukhari made an incomparable contribution to world science and culture. Enhancing the sense of pride in being the descendant of a thinker, the inheritor of a unique heritage, makes spirituality moral serves to develop thinking.

CONCLUSION. In short, it reflects the history of our country and our national cultural values preserving our historical and cultural monuments and widely promoting them among the youth of our compatriots especially in the hearts of young people, national pride, pride, love for the motherland, and the feeling of being proud of ancestors serves to increase the national value and moral thinking concepts in the minds of our youth helps them to deeply understand the true essence of Islam.

REFERENCES:

1. Number 217 29.04.1997 "Celebrating the birth of Imam al-Bukhari according to the Hijri-lunar calendar on "Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers.
2. National database of legal documents, April 15, 2020.
3. "Ethics of Islam" by Abdurahman Qaya, "Movorounnahr" publishing house T 1997.
4. Islam Karimov's work "High Spirituality-Invincible Power" T 2008.
5. Adambaev, U.Kh. (2022). CONFIDENCE FORMATION THE PLACE OF ARGUMENTATION.